

EXPLORING INNOVATIVE METHODS AND THE CHALLENGE OF MODULAR LEARNING IN SOUND DESIGN TEACHING

Nargiza Ismatullayevna Sadikova

State Institute of Art and Culture of Uzbekistan,
"Sound directing and cinematography skills"
teacher of the department

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Somewhat reinforcing the trend, attention is drawn to the fact that the information approach in relation to the educational process today is innovative and requires modern pedagogical and information-computer technology. Thus it is pointed out that traditionally, in the organisation of the learning process, it was assumed that announcing the name of an academic discipline was enough, and it immediately became clear to everyone what that knowledge was and what its content was. However, it has long been clear that in our rapidly developing world, knowledge itself and, perhaps more importantly, even attitudes to knowledge are constantly changing.¹

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¹https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=i_O1s8IAAAAJ&citation_for_view=i_O1s8IAAAAJ:Y0pCki6q_DkC **Creative researches of young cameramen on the creation of graphic image in modern uzbek feature films**

M Ikboljon, KS Tirkashaliyevich

ABSTRACT

This article explores innovative teaching methods that give effective results in the educational process, as well as a number of tasks and through which an analysis of the pedagogical problems of teaching the discipline of "Mastery of sound engineering" has been conducted.

The Law on Education of the Republic of Uzbekistan (Article 14. Higher Education) states: Higher education is aimed at training highly qualified specialists. Specialists with higher education are trained in institutions of higher education (universities, academies, institutes and other institutions of higher education) on the basis of specialized, vocational secondary education.

The most important and complex issue of pedagogy in higher education institutions is the optimization of the training process for future specialists, the development of professional qualifications, the creation of a new system of professional orientation, and the training of competent specialists. New forms and methods of training are needed to train such personnel. The use of innovative learning methods produces effective results in the educational process.

Innovative teaching methods contribute to the quality training of

specialists, who are able to widely apply the acquired knowledge in enterprises.

Learning process activation - building such a learning process, which involves organizing the learning process on a scientific basis, creating conditions for creative thinking, research work of students, forming interest in their future specialty, etc.

In the era of information technology, a specialist should be a creative person who has mastered the basics of computer technology, freely uses the possibilities of new technologies, is able to conduct independent research work and carry out diagnostic analysis of his/her work. For this reason, it is important for modern education system to apply pedagogical innovations and use interactive methods in educational process effectively and properly.

The most important part of education is to teach students to think independently, to accept and assimilate the material presented. The future of our country's potential specialists mainly depends on students' independent studies and teachers' competence. Teaching special disciplines in higher education institutions includes exploring opportunities and ways of studying selected disciplines at a professional level, studying modern teaching methods and the possibility of obtaining available skills to apply them, as well as, working out methods of final control of students' knowledge, special disciplines.

The learning process in higher education institutions should encourage students (bachelors, specialists, masters, etc.) to use the knowledge acquired in practice and in their tasks. It is also important for the teacher to present the topics of his or her

disciplines in higher education institution in a competent manner. The teacher should take into account the individual characteristics of the students, their age, and the degree of workload.

An integral part of the development of sound engineering has been the accumulation and consolidation of the theoretical knowledge reflected in the works of academics.

The Sound Engineering module builds the foundations for scientific and technical research into the production of sound, both as an individual and as part of a group with audio-visual projects. The theoretical material presented touches upon modern sound equipment development in film, television and radio implementation based on domestic and foreign experience. Forms fundamental skills of students in realization of their creative ideas in audiovisual genres by means of modern sound and computer technologies.

The development of modern technology, allows teachers to apply new learning processes. This is due to rapidly evolving computer technology. Thus, a need has arisen for new learning technologies that allow for flexible planning of learning time and taking into account the individual characteristics of students, ensuring the development and formation of their professional competences. The holistic nature of competences implies the integrity of their learning, which, in its turn, requires a fundamentally different approach to the selection of educational programme content and the integration of theory learning and practical skills acquisition into the learning process, as well as new principles and assessment methods. All these factors together constitute the

essence of competency-based modular education technology.

The relevance of modular learning has a programmatic approach to the construction of learning, gives the possibility of flexible approach at individual request, denies students receiving separate fragments of knowledge, gives in-depth knowledge of the system of scientific concepts, laws and phenomena. The focus of modular learning makes it possible to plan and organise the learning process, develop new methods and, most importantly, there is an opportunity to develop students' skills so that they contribute to a high degree of activity and conscientiousness.

The aim of the module is to educate and train the skills of a sound engineer, where the basis is to teach the essential quality of recording live sound and noise using innovative pedagogical techniques. To prepare a highly qualified specialist with all the artistic and technical means of a modern sound engineer for independent professional activity and teaching.

The objectives of the module are:

1. to study by students, the features of sound recording in two aspects: technical and artistic (creative).
2. Systematisation of the skills of sound control in the audio and digital transmission path.
3. Research methods: analysis, systematization and synthesis of methodological approaches, to the development of sound control skills of the students of the State Institute of Sound Engineering.
4. Application of innovative pedagogical technologies in teaching sound engineering of cinema, television and radio. The advantages of using the practical value of

the study of modular training methods, for the formation of the necessary professional competencies of students, is carried out:

- differentiated approach in training, taking into account the individual characteristics of the student and the group as a whole;
- possibility to use different ways of activity organisation (individual, in pairs, in groups);
- a more holistic and clearly structured understanding of the material;
- Increasing the level of students' professional competence;
- increased motivation in the study of the discipline due to the inclusion of each student in the learning process;

The conducted research allows us to make a conclusion about the relevance of updating the education system through a modular approach.

The following technologies can be attributed to the tested pedagogical technologies to ensure the effectiveness of the process of final assessment of students' mastering of the training direction "Sound engineering in cinema, TV and radio", integral educational module, in particular: problem-based learning technology, construction of logical and semantic models, case-study, scientific discussion, solving situational tasks, presentations, actualization of the educational process subjects' potential.² The module is aimed

²https://scholar.google.ru/citations?view_op=view_citation&hl=ru&user=i_O1s8IAAAAJ&citation_for_view=i_O1s8IAAAAJ:qUcmZB5y_30C [Современная медиакультура как фактор глобализации в искусстве](#)

И Меликузиев
Ученые записки (Алтайская государственная академия культуры и искусств), 123–124.

at mastering the discipline and solving problems of pedagogical education, with the help of modern pedagogical technologies, which allows the use of

innovative computer technologies: Internet, Internet resources, training sites, multimedia.

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